

antifragiCity

June 2025

PRESS RELEASE

Building 'antifragile' cities: AntifragiCity project launches to strengthen urban mobility systems across Europe

- AntifragiCity aims to reshape how cities respond to disruptions — paving the way for mobility systems that become stronger under pressure.
- For 36 months, 13 partners from 8 countries will work together to reimagine urban resilience in a time of rapid change and uncertainty.
- Pilot projects in Larissa, Odessa, Bratislava, and Thessaloniki will explore how different urban settings can benefit from 'antifragile' mobility solutions in real-life conditions.

The consortium of **AntifragiCity**, a €4 million project funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe programme, is proud to announce its official launch. This pioneering research and innovation initiative aims to help cities across Europe develop mobility systems that not only withstand disruption but also adapt and improve through it.

Over the next three years, 13 partners from 8 countries will collaborate to apply this approach in real-world settings. Pilot projects in Larissa (Greece), Odessa (Ukraine), Bratislava (Slovakia), and Thessaloniki (Greece) will test tools, models, and strategies for building more robust and responsive transport systems. The findings will inform future EU-wide strategies and policies.

The consortium, coordinated by Cardiff University, brings together municipalities, research institutions, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and innovation labs. The official kick-off meeting took place on 14–15 May 2025 in Thessaloniki, hosted by the Greek mobility company Rhoé.

Funded by
the European Union

From resilience to ‘antifragility’

Traditional approaches that focus on restoring stability are no longer enough. The project introduces the concept of ‘antifragility’ into urban planning — an approach that goes beyond resilience. Rather than simply recovering from disruption, **antifragile systems use stress as a driver for learning, adaptation, and long-term improvement.** AntifragiCity applies this thinking to urban mobility, aiming to shift how cities respond to crisis and change, supporting the transition toward more sustainable, equitable, and resilient urban environments across Europe.

“In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, the energy crisis, and an ongoing war in Europe, cities are facing unprecedented challenges. AntifragiCity is about harnessing these disruptions as catalysts for positive change, building urban systems that adapt, learn, and emerge stronger. By integrating technology with local knowledge and citizen participation, we aim to pave the way to sustainable cities that are not only resilient but truly antifragile,” says Project Coordinator Yacine Rezgui, Professor of Urban Intelligence at the Cardiff University School of Engineering.

The project will develop new frameworks and simulation tools to monitor stress in transport networks, predict and manage disruptions, and support rapid response. It will also test long-term measures, such as dynamic traffic systems and predictive analytics. These tools will help European cities design inclusive, robust, and future-ready mobility systems, addressing both short-term shocks and long-term challenges.

The AntifragiCity consortium

The project brings together a multidisciplinary team of 13 partners from Greece, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Spain, Slovakia, Switzerland, the UK, and Ukraine. The consortium blends expertise in transport engineering, public policy, urban planning, social sciences, public health, and citizen engagement.

Partners include: Cardiff University, Rhoé, DEMO Consultants, LISER, IED, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, National Technical University of Athens, ETH Zurich, Municipality of Larissa, Metropolitan Institute of Bratislava, Odessa 5T, AHEPA University General Hospital of Thessaloniki, and AUSTRALO.

The AntifragiCity partners at the project's kick-off meeting, hosted by Rhoé.

Get in touch

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Disclaimer: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101203052. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.